

economía circular. Durante tres misiones se analizaron dos escenarios de saneamiento: (i) letrinas de pozo no mejoradas existentes y (ii) un sistema alternativo basado en inodoros secos separadores de orina (UDDT) con sanitización amoniacal de las heces (cal, cenizas y urea) y tratamiento de la orina en un círculo plantado. Los resultados demostraron que los UDDT pueden mejorar significativamente la seguridad, mitigar los riesgos de contaminación de las aguas subterráneas y facilitar la recuperación de nutrientes para fines agrícolas. La participación comunitaria fue central en la implementación, con adaptaciones locales como la sustitución de bananos por papayas en el círculo de tratamiento de orina. Los principales desafíos incluyeron la logística, el suministro de materiales y la necesidad de monitoreo continuo. A pesar de estas dificultades, la iniciativa mostró que las tecnologías adaptadas localmente pueden promover la salud, la protección ambiental y beneficios socioeconómicos. Esta experiencia resalta la importancia de la cooperación Sur-Sur y proporciona un modelo replicable para otras comunidades rurales en África Subsahariana y contextos similares.

Palabras clave: Recuperación de agua y nutrientes; África Subsahariana; Saneamiento seguro

RESUMO

Este relato de experiência apresenta o processo de implementação de alternativas de saneamento seguro em Bandiagara II, uma comunidade produtora de algodão no sul do Mali, no âmbito da cooperação Sul-Sul entre Brasil e Mali. O objetivo principal foi oferecer uma solução de saneamento viável e adaptada ao contexto local, assegurando a proteção das águas subterráneas, bem como a recuperação de água e nutrientes. O contexto da experiência foi marcado por graves desafios de saneamento na região do Sahel, onde predominam as latrinas rudimentares não melhoradas. Essas latrinas representam riscos à saúde devido à contaminação do lençol freático e à limitada economia circular. Durante três missões foram analisados dois cenários de saneamento: (i) latrinas rudimentares existentes e (ii) um sistema alternativo baseado em banheiros secos separadores de urina (UDDT) com sanitização amoniacal das fezes (cal, cinzas e ureia) e tratamento da urina em círculo plantado. Os resultados demonstraram que os UDDT podem melhorar significativamente a segurança, reduzir os riscos de contaminação das águas subterráneas e facilitar a recuperação de nutrientes para fins agrícolas. A participação comunitária foi central na implementação, com adaptações locais como a substituição da bananeira pela mamoeira no círculo de tratamento da urina. Os principais desafios incluíram a logística, o fornecimento de materiais e a necessidade de monitoramento contínuo. Apesar dessas dificuldades, a iniciativa mostrou que tecnologias adaptadas localmente podem promover saúde, proteção ambiental e benefícios socioeconômicos. Esta experiência evidencia a importância da cooperação Sul-Sul e fornece um modelo replicável para outras comunidades rurais da África Subsaariana e contextos semelhantes.

Palavras-chave: Reuso de água e nutrientes, esgotamento sanitário seguro, África Subsaariana

DESCRIPTION OF THE EXPERIENCE

Originally from the Bandiagara Cliffs near Mopti, at the centre of the Mali, the Dogon people migrated to Bandiagara II due to conflicts in the north. The village is now geographically situated in the Koutiala region and has an estimated population of 630 inhabitants (Figure 1). It lies in a semi-arid climate. Annual rainfall ranges between 600 and 900 mm, supporting primarily rainfed cotton as the main crop, followed by cereals and livestock (World Bank, 2023). Cooperation between Brazil and Mali is facilitated through the CMDT and the Brazilian Cooperation Agency (ABC), with a focus on increasing cotton production (Agência Brasileira de Cooperação ABC, 2024). In this process, the need for health and sanitation care in villages has become a path to improve producers' quality of life. Over three one-week missions, we assessed the sanitation system, including latrines, faecal sludge emptying,

transport, usage, and water supply from hand wells. We also discussed and implemented the UDDTs.

Figure 1. Bandiagara II village drone photography, where the nuclei organization can be seen.
Source: Authors, 2024.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The existing sanitation system consists of unimproved pit latrines used for defecation, which are approximately 3 meters deep and are typically in use for 2 years. After that period, they are closed with a piece of wood and left to rest for another year (Figure 2). After that, the faeces are transported by handcart and used in the family's agricultural field. The urine runs down the superstructure walls and remains on the floor surface, posing epidemiological risks and creating an unpleasant odour.

Figure 2. Existing scenario observed in the village of Bandiagara II, where unhygienic latrines are located near water supply wells, with the risk of groundwater contamination. Source: Authors, 2024.

The alternative system consists of Urine Diverting Dry Toilets (UDDT), where faeces are contained in buckets of 50 L, and treated using ammonium-based sanitization through a 1:1 mix of lime and ash (130 g/person) with 2% urea to elevate the pH and closed for two months, inactivating pathogens for safe soil use (Magri, 2015). Urine (from urinals) and anal cleansing are conducted through flexible hoses to a planted circle for land-based treatment and nutrient recovery (Figueiredo et al., 2018). Additionally, a local hand-wash basin was installed near the toilet to promote good hygiene practices. The grey water is used to pour flush the urine through the hose into the plant circle (Figure 3).

Figure 3. UDDT community installation, usage, and monitoring
Source: Authors, 2024.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This experience demonstrated that UDDTs with plant circles can be implemented in rural villages of Mali to enhance water and nutrient recovery by segregating and treating excreta for proper use. The buckets' containment prevents underground water contamination and simplifies safe emptying and transport (E&T), especially after the treatment period. Handwash water can be used for flushing urine, which, combined, helps with papaya production by infiltration, avoiding standing water and vector spread. This experience highlights the role of South–South cooperation in addressing complex challenges in vulnerable regions and provides a replicable model for other rural communities in Sub-Saharan Africa.

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